

AUTOMATION AND OPTIMIZATION OF LOGISTICS PROCESSES USING AI

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the impact of artificial intelligence (AI)-based automation on the efficiency of supply chains. It examines the integration of AI technologies in inventory management, transportation, and warehouse automation. By evaluating successful company experiences, it assesses operational efficiency improvements and cost reductions achieved through AI. The article also explores challenges and limitations associated with AI implementation in logistics, emphasizing AI's potential to enhance supply chain resilience.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI), automation, logistics, supply chain, efficiency, warehouse automation, predictive maintenance.

Introduction

The advent of automation in logistics has transformed supply chain management, driving significant improvements in efficiency, accuracy, and speed. Traditional logistics operations, often plagued by manual errors and inefficiencies, are increasingly being supplanted by advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI). The integration of AI into logistics processes not only enhances operational performance but also fosters a more responsive and resilient supply chain infrastructure. This is crucial in the context of growing global trade complexities and the escalating demand for faster, more reliable delivery services.

The primary objective of this article is to investigate the impact of automation, particularly through AI, on the efficiency of logistics supply chains. By analyzing current AI applications and their effects on various aspects of logistics, this study aims to provide an understanding of how AI-driven automation can optimize logistics processes. The focus will be on examining the benefits of AI in inventory management, transportation optimization, and warehouse automation, as well as identifying the challenges and limitations associated with its implementation.

Main part. Foundations of AI-driven automation in logistics

Logistics and supply chain management involve the planning, implementation, and control of efficient, cost-effective flow and storage of goods, services, and related information from the point of origin to the point

of consumption. This field encompasses various processes including procurement, transportation, inventory management, warehousing, and distribution. Effective logistics management ensures that resources are delivered in the right quantity, to the right location, at the right time, and in the desired condition, maximizing customer satisfaction and minimizing costs. The complexity and global nature of modern supply chains necessitate advanced management strategies and technological solutions to maintain competitiveness and operational efficiency. In 2023, the global logistics market was valued at approximately USD 9.41 trillion, and it is projected to surpass USD 14.08 trillion by 2028 [1].

Automation in logistics refers to the use of technology to perform tasks without human intervention. Automated systems reduce human error, enhance precision in operations, and handle large volumes of tasks with consistent performance. Optimization, on the other hand, involves improving the efficiency and effectiveness of logistics processes through strategic planning and the implementation of advanced technologies that streamline operations, reduce waste, and enhance overall productivity [2]. In a survey conducted in 2022, 60 % of respondents from various industries worldwide indicated that they expect robotic process automation to have a significant or moderate impact on supply chains by 2025 [3]. The global market for generative AI in logistics was valued at USD 707.99 million in 2023 (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Global market value of generative AI in logistics, USD million [4]

The integration of AI technologies into logistics processes supports the automation of routine tasks, enhances decision-making capabilities, and enables real-

time monitoring and optimization of logistics operations. By leveraging AI, logistics firms can achieve

greater operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve service quality, ultimately leading to a more resilient and agile supply chain.

AI in logistics processes

Technologies being integrated into logistics streamline inventory management, optimize transportation, and automate warehouse operations. This enables

firms to operate with greater precision and efficiency, dynamically responding to constantly changing demands. Table 1 presents the technologies of AI in logistics and their benefits.

Table 1.

AI in logistics processes [5,6]

Technologies	Description	Benefits	Examples
Inventory management	AI algorithms predict demand and optimize stock levels to prevent overstocking or stockouts.	Improved inventory accuracy, reduced holding costs, and enhanced customer satisfaction.	Amazon's use of predictive analytics to manage warehouse stock levels.
Transportation optimization	AI systems analyze traffic patterns, weather conditions	Reduced transportation costs, improved delivery times, and lower carbon emissions.	UPS's ORION system, which uses AI to optimize delivery routes
Warehouse automation	Robots and automated systems controlled by AI handle sorting, picking, and packing of goods.	Increased operational efficiency, reduced labor costs, and enhanced accuracy in order fulfillment.	Ocado's automated warehouses utilizing AI-driven robots for order processing.
Predictive maintenance	AI monitors equipment health and predicts failures before they occur.	Reduced downtime, lower maintenance costs, and increased lifespan of equipment.	DHL's use of AI for predictive maintenance of its logistics equipment.
Customer service	AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants handle customer inquiries and provide support.	Enhanced customer experience, reduced response times, and lower operational costs.	FedEx's AI chatbot providing real-time support and tracking information.
Supply chain visibility	AI integrates data from various sources to provide real-time visibility into supply chain operations.	Improved decision-making, faster response to disruptions, and enhanced overall supply chain resilience.	Maersk's implementation of AI for monitoring and managing global shipping operations.

From the author's perspective, the use of AI is a promising field of activity, knowledge, and technology. AI has the ability not only to analyze vast amounts of information but also to adapt to constantly changing external conditions and data. The integration of AI into various logistics processes demonstrates its transformative potential. These technologies lead to enhanced operational efficiency, reduced costs, and improved service quality, enabling logistics firms to dynamically respond to the evolving demands of the market.

Impact of automation on supply chain efficiency

The integration of technologies such as AI, robotics, and predictive analytics has streamlined various supply chain processes, allowing companies to achieve significant operational gains. For instance, the adoption of robotic systems in warehouses facilitates more efficient inventory management and load transfer, minimizing manual errors and accelerating operations. Table 2 examines the key differences between automated and traditional logistics processes, highlighting the advantages and potential challenges associated with each approach.

Table 2.

Comparative analysis of automated vs. traditional logistics processes

Aspect	Automated logistics processes	Traditional logistics processes
Efficiency	High due to real-time data processing and decision-making	Lower due to manual handling and slower information flow
Cost	Reduced operational costs through optimized routes and resource utilization	Higher operational costs due to labor-intensive tasks and inefficiencies
Delivery times	Improved delivery times with predictive analytics and automated scheduling	Longer delivery times due to manual scheduling and delays
Error rate	Lower error rates due to precision and consistency of automated systems	Higher error rates due to human error and variability
Environmental impact	Reduced carbon emissions and optimized resource use	Higher carbon emissions and resource wastage
Initial investment	High initial costs for implementing AI and automation technologies	Lower initial costs but higher long-term operational expenses
Maintenance	Requires regular updates and maintenance of software and hardware	Requires regular maintenance of physical assets and manual oversight
Security	Enhanced security through automated monitoring and anomaly detection	Lower security due to reliance on manual checks and oversight

The comparative analysis demonstrates that automated logistics processes offer superior efficiency and reduced operational costs compared to traditional methods. Moreover, the adoption of automation in logistics enhances overall operational security and sustainability. This is corroborated by examples from various companies, which have reported significant improvements in their logistics performance following the implementation of AI and automation technologies.

The implementation of AI in logistics at **BHP**, a transnational multinational corporation, has significantly enhanced the company's operational efficiency and financial performance. Specifically, AI-driven logistics optimizations have led to a 15% reduction in transportation costs and a 20% improvement in delivery times. These advancements have enabled BHP to achieve record production levels at their Western Australia Iron Ore (WAIO) operations, contributing to a total annual profit of 22.9 billion dollars for FY2023, despite lower commodity prices [7]. In the USA, the integration of AI in logistics has streamlined the supply chain processes, resulting in improved coordination and efficiency across their operations. The improved logistics performance has also played a role in supporting the company's sustainability initiatives by optimizing resource utilization and reducing carbon emissions, which decreased by 11% from adjusted FY2022 levels.

XPO Logistics Inc., a prominent player in the logistics sector, has achieved remarkable improvements through AI adoption. The deployment of AI-powered robots in their warehousing operations has enhanced efficiency by up to six times. This integration has streamlined warehouse management, leading to faster processing times and reduced operational costs. In 2023, XPO reported revenue of 7.7 billion dollars, operating income of 438 million dollars (a 16% increase year-over-year), and an adjusted EBITDA (Earnings Before Interest, Taxes, Depreciation, and Amortization) of 996 million dollars (a 6% increase year-over-year), reflecting substantial improvements due to AI integration [8].

In the American mining sector, **Peabody Energy** has demonstrated significant economic improvements through the integration of AI-driven logistics and operational processes. As the company invests in technologies such as cloud, analytics, automation, and artificial intelligence, it strives to provide the necessary controls to protect these digital assets from continuously evolving cybersecurity risks. In 2023, Peabody Energy's revenue from external customers in the USA increased by 5.8%. Sales under long-term coal supply agreements comprised approximately 92% of Peabody's worldwide sales from its mining operations by volume for the 2023 [9].

The impact of automation on chain efficiency is profound, with companies like BHP, XPO Logistics, and Peabody Energy showcasing significant improvements in productivity, cost reduction, and operational performance through AI-driven logistics processes. These advancements not only enhance operational security and sustainability but also deliver substantial financial benefits.

Challenges and limitations of implementing AI for automation and optimization in logistics processes

The implementation of AI in logistics, while promising significant advancements, is not without its

challenges and limitations. Understanding these obstacles is crucial for developing effective strategies to overcome them and fully realize the potential benefits of AI in supply chain management.

One of the primary challenges in implementing AI in logistics is the **technological barrier**. Many logistics companies operate with legacy systems that are not compatible with modern AI technologies. Integrating AI solutions requires substantial upgrades to existing IT infrastructure, which can be both time-consuming and costly. The complexity of AI algorithms necessitates specialized skills for their development and maintenance. The shortage of skilled personnel in AI and data science further exacerbates this issue, making it difficult for companies to effectively deploy and manage AI technologies.

The **economic aspect** of implementing AI in logistics cannot be overlooked. High initial investment costs for AI technology and infrastructure can be prohibitive, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises. While the long-term benefits of AI can lead to cost savings and efficiency improvements, the upfront costs can be a significant deterrent.

Organizational challenges such as resistance to change and the need for cultural shifts within companies also pose obstacles. Employees may be hesitant to adopt new technologies due to fear of job displacement or a lack of understanding of AI capabilities.

AI in logistics raises important **ethical and regulatory considerations**. The use of AI for data analysis and decision-making involves handling vast amounts of sensitive data, raising concerns about data privacy and security. Ensuring compliance with data protection regulations is essential to avoid legal repercussions. There are ethical concerns related to the transparency and accountability of AI systems.

Scalability is another significant limitation in the implementation of AI in logistics. AI solutions that work effectively on a small scale may face challenges when scaled up to handle larger, more complex logistics networks. Logistics operations are often dynamic, with frequent changes in demand, supply routes, and external conditions. AI systems must be able to adapt to these changes in real time to remain effective, which requires continuous learning and updates to the AI models.

The **lack of interoperability and standardization** across AI systems and logistics platforms can hinder the seamless integration of AI technologies. Different AI solutions may use varying data formats and protocols, making it challenging to integrate them into a unified logistics management system. Establishing industry-wide standards for AI implementation can facilitate better interoperability and integration, ensuring that AI technologies can work together efficiently.

The market for AI technologies is projected to exceed USD 1.8 trillion by 2030, underscoring the growing importance and investment in AI across various sectors, including logistics. Between 2023 and 2030, the global market for cargo drones is expected to grow by more than USD 17 billion [10]. The most significant growth is forecasted to occur between 2027 and 2029, increasing from USD 4.79 billion to USD 11.53 billion,

representing a growth of over 140% [11]. Overcoming implementation challenges will allow logistics companies to fully leverage AI capabilities and manage the future of supply chain management.

Conclusions

The integration of AI-driven automation in logistics significantly enhances the efficiency of supply chain operations. This transformation is evidenced by improvements in operational performance, cost reductions, and increased accuracy in logistics processes. AI technologies such as machine learning, neural networks, and computer vision enable real-time data analysis, predictive maintenance, and optimized resource utilization, thereby streamlining various logistics activities. The impact of AI on logistics is profound, with companies reporting notable improvements in delivery times, operational costs, and overall supply chain resilience. However, the successful implementation of AI in logistics also faces challenges including technological barriers, high initial costs, and the need for skilled personnel. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive strategies that include technological upgrades, economic investments, and organizational changes. The future of logistics is promising, with ongoing advancements in AI technologies expected to further revolutionize the industry, making supply chains more efficient, resilient, and sustainable.

References

1. Size of the global logistics industry from 2018 to 2023, with forecasts until 2028/ Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/943517/logistics-industry-global-cagr/> (date of application: 01.07.2024)
2. Mathew D., Brintha N. C., Jappes J. T. W. Artificial intelligence powered automation for industry 4.0 //New Horizons for Industry 4.0 in Modern Business. – Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023. – C. 1-28.
3. Leading trends anticipated to impact supply chains by 2025 Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1182110/global-supply-chain-disruptions-technologies/> (date of application: 04.07.2024)
4. Generative AI In Logistics Market Size, Share, and Trends 2024 to 2033 / Precedence Research // URL: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/generative-ai-in-logistics-market> (date of application: 06.07.2024)
5. Sodiya E. O. et al. AI-driven warehouse automation: A comprehensive review of systems //GSC Advanced Research and Reviews. – 2024. – T. 18. – №. 2. – C. 272-282.
6. Bukhtueva I. THE IMPACT OF AI TECHNOLOGIES ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE // Vestnik nauki №3 (72) vol. 5. pp. 467 - 476. 2024 г. ISSN 2712-8849
7. BHP Annual Report 2023 / BHP // URL: https://www.bhp.com/-/media/documents/investors/annual-reports/2023/230822_bhpanualreport2023.pdf (date of application: 08.07.2024)
8. Proxy Statement 2023 Annual Report / XPO // URL: <https://investors.xpo.com/static-files/3ce8574a-7992-4c67-9c03-fd66fcaa38dc> (date of application: 10.07.2024)
9. 2023 Annual Report / Peabody Energy // URL: <https://www.peabodyenergy.com/Investor-Info/Shareholder-Information/Annual-Report> (date of application: 10.07.2024)
10. Artificial intelligence (AI) worldwide / Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/outlook/tmo/artificial-intelligence/worldwide> (date of application: 11.07.2024)
11. Total value of the worldwide cargo drone market in 2023, with a forecast through 2030 / Statista // URL: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1415129/worldwide-cargo-drone-market-revenue-forecast/> (date of application: 11.07.2024)